

Live Demonstration of a Trimodal Time-of-Flight Camera with Enhanced Material Imaging

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Abstract—Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras retrieve the 3D geometry of the world by leveraging the fact that time delays of photons interacting with the latter encode distance. To this end, ToF cameras probe the scene with modulated light and use an array of time-resolved pixels to demodulate the return. As noted in recent works, different materials exhibit different impulse response functions to modulated light and this can be exploited for recognizing them. In this demonstrator we showcase a trimodal ToF camera, able to deliver dense NIR intensity, depth, and material images in real time with unprecedented quality. The system implements novel strategies to boost robustness, while coping with misclassification in boundary regions.

Index Terms—Time-of-Flight, material sensing, MIRF, 3D neural networks, spatial correlation

I. INTRODUCTION

The delay experienced by individual photons when interacting with a particular material depends on the nature of the material itself and on the geometry of the interface between the material and the medium (e. g., its roughness). Owing to this fact, when a material is probed with modulated light, the corresponding light bounce does not exactly follow the initial modulation pattern, but the result of a convolution with an impulse response function (IRF) that is given by the probability density function of the time delay that the material induced on the photons. Provided that Time-of-Flight (ToF) pixels are endowed with time resolved capabilities, they can be used to obtain measurements of this *material IRF* (MIRF), from which relevant features for material classification can be extracted. This was proposed in [1] to distinguish materials with markedly different surface and sub-surface scattering properties and further studied in [2], [3]. In [2] an off-the-shelf Microsoft Xbox One Kinect (v2) sensor is used, what restricts the number of modulation frequencies to three and precludes access to raw data. The scarcity of sampling points in frequency domain is compensated by acquiring multiple measurements at different distances between the camera and the scene. Differently, [3] uses frequency sampling to obtain Fourier measurements of the MIRF and unveils a *trimodal camera*, able to simultaneously deliver streams of NIR intensity, depth, and material images. The attractiveness of such sensor relies on the complementary information delivered by the individual modalities: a depth modality allows for distinguishing *camouflaged* objects based on their geometry, while a material modality allows distinguishing objects that

may exhibit both similar texture and geometry, but are of different material, e. g., a human face and a latex mask.

II. LIVE DEMONSTRATION OF A TRIMODAL TOF CAMERA

This demo builds upon [4], which aimed to demonstrate the feasibility of the trimodal ToF camera concept, but also showed limited performance in the generation of the material modality, which was based on Support Vector Machines (SVM). The use of SVMs made necessary it to introduce super-pixel-based classification in order to attain high frame rates. This compromised the geometrical accuracy of the reconstructed material images and the detection of tiny objects or inclusions of other materials. In this demo, the following enhancements have been introduced:

- **Neural networks** (NNs) have been used as classifiers to speed up inference without loss of classification accuracy, as suggested in [3]. Differently from [3], local correlations between neighboring pixels are leveraged to boost classification accuracy.
- The use of NNs avoids the need for clustering and allows for dense **pixelwise material classification**, thus solving the limitations of [4].
- Considering a spatial neighborhood yields 3D features, exhibiting two more dimensions than those used in [4]. This calls for a matching **3D NN architecture**.
- A method has been developed to increase **robustness** while coping with **boundary regions**. This method uses a bilateral weighting scheme over a local neighborhood concatenated with a K nearest neighbors (KNN) search in feature space.

The setup that will be demonstrated consists of a PMD Selene ToF module with custom firmware observing a multi-material test scene, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The test scene can feature up to five different materials simultaneously, namely foam board, polystyrene, bubble wrap, crepe paper, and wax. Some materials may be removed and placed again to test functionality. The test scene is mounted on a stage. Both this stage and the ToF module are mounted on carriers on an X95 aluminium optical rail. This allows for adjusting their location on the rail and, thus, the relative distance between them, while keeping the setup mechanically stable. The visitor will be allowed to interact with the setup, by displacing or rotating it, and also by adding or removing some materials.

Fig. 1: Setup developed for the live demonstration of our trimodal camera. The ToF camera (right) observes a heterogeneous scene composed by instances of five different materials (foam board, polystyrene, bubble wrap, crepe paper, and wax), placed at approximately the same distance from the camera. The optical rail and the carriers on top of which both camera and target scene are mounted allow for adjustment of the relative position and orientation.

(a) RGB image of test scene

(b) NIR amplitude image

(c) Depth image

(d) Material image

Fig. 2: Test scene used in our demonstrator (a) and screenshots of the NIR amplitude (b), depth (c), and material (d) images delivered by our trimodal camera. The test materials are foam board, polystyrene, bubble wrap, crepe paper, and wax. The dominant color for each test object in (d) corresponds to the right material, i.e., yellow, cyan, red, green, and blue, respectively. Depth scale in meters.

Fig. 2 presents the test setup used in our demonstrator (Fig. 2a), together with samples of the streams of NIR amplitude, depth, and material images delivered by our trimodal ToF camera. Fig. 2 bears witness to the complementarity of the different sensing modalities. The absence of texture in all materials except from the bubble wrap in Fig. 2a invalidates classical material recognition approaches based on RGB image patches. The NIR modality (Fig. 2b) could be combined

with the RGB modality to attempt classification based on multispectral signatures, but this would require an additional RGB sensor and classification accuracy would suffer from a scarce number of bands. The depth image (Fig. 2c) describes the 3D geometry and should thus be independent from both intensity and material nature. In our setup all materials are placed at approximately the same distance from the sensor. The material image (Fig. 2d) showcases the good per-pixel classification attained by our approach and features sharp borders between materials that are not clearly observable in either the NIR amplitude image or the material image.

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